

SMEs Competitiveness Development in Small Industrial Village (PIK) of Pulogadung by Government Agency as a Public Sector

Roselina Lathi Putri Rusarditya¹, M. Syamsul Maarif², Setiadi Djohar³

^{1,2}IPB University, School of Business, Jl Raya Pajajaran, Bogor, Indonesia

³PPM School of Management, Jl Menteng Raya, Jakarta, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Roselina Lathi Putri Rusarditya

ABSTRACT

Small Industrial Village (PIK) of Pulogadung is the center of SMEs in East Jakarta, Indonesia, and managed by Management Unit of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises Development Centers and Pulogadung Settlements (UPK PPUKMP) which is a government agency to assist SMEs. The research aims to analyze strategies in financial perspectives, customer perspectives, internal business process perspectives, and learning & growth perspectives, and also to recommend priorities strategies in the development of SMEs in PIK Pulogadung. The data collection methods are in-depth interviews and survey techniques. The data analysis method was done using a Balanced Scorecard to describe strategic objectives and AHP to weight against strategic target priorities. Based on AHP's weighted results, the customer perspective ranks first in the strategic priority of the 52,0%, followed by a learning and growth perspective of 26,3%, an internal business process perspective of 14,0%, and the last is financial perspective of 7,7%. The strategic goal of the financial perspective that has the greatest weight is the increase in independence by 67,2% weight. The customer perspective with the largest weight value is the strategic target of 84,8%. The strategic goal of internal business process perspective which has the largest weight is an effective business process improvement, with a weighted value of 45,9%. The strategic objective of the most significant learning and growth that has the greatest weight is the increase in the competency of human resources, with a weight value of 82,5%.

Keywords: AHP, balanced scorecard, SMEs

INTRODUCTION

The opportunities opening and the increasingly free community to conduct business activities will have an impact on the Indonesian economy, especially in terms of trade. A factor that can widely be supporting product trade is the adoption of the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC). The four pillars in the establishment and implementation of the AEC are to make ASEAN as the area of production base area and single market, the area having competitiveness, area promoting equitable economic development, and Area integrated with global markets.

Bank Indonesia (2016) states that ASEAN as an area promoting economic development is the third pillar of the AEC, aims to build Micro, Small & Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) in ASEAN to become one having competitiveness, being firmer, and having a big contribution to the ASEAN economy. However, in terms of operational and supporting activities, the MSMEs development institutions in Indonesia are still unstable. Many programs are not sustainable, such as Business Development Centers. This Business Development Center has been built in 1,096 locations throughout Indonesia, but their existence has not existed anymore.

Furthermore, Bank Indonesia (2016) states that so far, government policies related to MSMEc use more social welfare approaches than business approaches. MSMEs are considered as vulnerable

business entities and require protection so that many government policies related to MSMEs that are providing protection which 'set line' MSMEs from the competition. Competition is a required environment for the growth and development of a company for having competitiveness.

According to Law No. 20 in 2008, the government plays a role in empowering and developing MSMEs. Within the law, article 1 paragraphs 8 and 10 states that the empowerment and development are efforts made by the government, business community, and the community in synergy to form climate growth and business development so that they can grow and develop through the provision of facilities, guidance, assistance, and reinforcement assistance. It is to grow and improve the ability and competitiveness of MSMEs. According to the Kemenkop and UKM (2015), efforts to empower SMEs are focused on two strategic issues, business growths, and competitiveness. Mariana (2008) states that the increase of the SME's competitiveness is still not optimal. SMEs are still struggling and have to struggle in maintaining the domestic market share which is now also the target market of other countries.

As one of the provinces supporting the Indonesian economy, DKI Jakarta has some potential areas that can be developed. One of them is Small Industrial Village (PIK) of Pulogadung managed by Management Unit of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises Development Centers and Pulogadung Settlements (UPK PPUKMPP). Local Government of East Jakarta said that PIK of Pulogadung has potentials as a trade area supporting the development of the SMEs industry, as a residential area having high density and productive housing, and as industrial tourism which can be used as an attraction to make the PIK area alive. However, based on Regional Regulation No. 1 of 2018 concerning on Regional Medium-term Development Plan (RPJMD) of DKI Jakarta of 2017-2022, it was explained that one of the regional challenges

in facing the AEC is to increase the competitiveness of regional superior products including the potential of the region itself, in this case, the potential of PIK area.

LITERATUR REVIEW

According to Tambunan (2009), generally, the low competitiveness of SMEs in developing countries can be a serious obstacle for the business group which is not only to be able to penetrate the global market but also to be able to win the competitive market with imported goods in the domestic market. In her study, Mariana (2008) stated that the competitiveness of SMEs sector in Indonesia, regionally, was lower than the SMEs sector in Thailand and Malaysia. Meanwhile, in dealing with China, it requires regional economic integration in the commitment of a single market and production base.

According to Soekarwo (2018), the government needs to provide support the SMEs in the form of technology and information strengthening, access to financial resources, and good market access as obtained by large enterprises. Furthermore, Soekarwo explained that it was necessary to do empowerment thoroughly, optimally, and continuously, through the development of a conducive climate to objectify economic growth, equity and increase of people income, job creation, and poverty alleviation. It is required to be done because SMEs have a strategic role to increase income and employment opportunities, reducing poverty, and expanding employment in Indonesia. Sunandar (2014) stated that it is necessary to increase cooperation with banks, to implement the policies of the central and regional government to achieve prosperity, and to implement regulations of central and local government to improve SMEs.

PIK area established by the government in the context of developing SMEs is fostered by the Provincial Government of DKI Jakarta and managed

by UPK PPUKMPP who is responsible to the Industry, Trade, Cooperatives, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (PPKUKM) Office of DKI Jakarta and implementing the Financial Management Pattern (PPK) of Regional Public Service Agency (BLUD). According to Pasaribu (2014), the implementation of PPK BLUD has a strategic issue, which is in the formation of BLUD, it has the main objective of improving the quality of service to the community. However, the question is how to know that the BLUD has achieved the expected goals because the BLUD is not run in the context of seeking profit but providing quality services to the community. This is a difficult challenge because BLUD are expected to not only be efficient and effective but also pay attention to access to services that can be reached by all levels of society. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct comprehensive performance management, so that the organization does not only focus on revenue but also focus on service users (customer-focus) and pay attention to the efficiency of business processes and employee satisfaction.

According to, Assauri (2013), in establishing competitive advantage must be carried out appropriately and sustainably, by developing strategies while implementing them. It can be done with proper organizing activities, starting with identification, strengthening the organization, and increasing the company's leadership capabilities. The Balanced Scorecard is one of the tools to develop a strategic plan that can describe into four more detailed perspectives. They are financial perspective, customer perspective, internal business process perspective, and learning & growth perspective. Mulyadi (2001) explained that the advantage in using the Balanced Scorecard as a strategic planning tool can produce strategic plans having comprehensive, coherent, balanced, and measurable characteristics.

Gaspersz (2002) explained that there are differences in the perspective of the

Balanced Scorecard applied to profit-oriented business organizations (private sector) and those applied to public service-oriented government organizations (public sector). The main focus of government organizations is not on achieving financial goals, but on achieving goals focusing on customers. In this context, it can be linked to the penitentiary residents. Praptomo (2017) explained that important aspects of public-sector accountability include accountability of hierarchy, professional, process, and finance. However, from the perspective of learning and growth, it needs to be reformulated to answer another essential aspect of accountability, which are motivation and empowerment of human resources. Fitriyani (2014) stated the implementation of the Balanced Scorecard can be modified and can adapt to the type of organization, vision, and strategy set.

According to Komaryati et al. (2018), the financial aspects of the financial perspective remain an integral part of every organizational performance. However, there is a perspective change in the financial perspective of the public sector. In public organizations, financial perspective is more directed at how organizations improve financial performance by the targets set by each agency effectively and efficiently.

Customer perspectives in the public sector or non-profit institutions can use customer satisfaction levels. According to Wijaya (1997), the customer satisfaction level is a customer feeling between customer expectations and the performance he/she experience. If the performance is below the expectations, the customer will feel disappointed or feel an improvement is required, while if the performance is above the expectations, the customer will be satisfied. It was further stated that service quality is a match between perceived service and customer expectation. A match between the two things will indicate the customer satisfaction levels, so that it can be said that when assessing service quality, customer satisfaction can also be identified.

According to Kopecka (2015), the internal business process perspective is the core in terms of achieving the success of the Balanced Scorecard strategy. One of which is paying attention to the operations management process or the business processes run. It means that paying attention to the efforts of providing goods and/or services to customers responsively are a must. Furthermore, in learning and growth perspective, it is necessary to interpret the employee's perspective focusing on the development of employee competencies.

METHODS

This study was conducted in Small Industrial Village (PIK) of Pulogadung. The location was purposely selected with the consideration that SMEs located in PIK of Pulogadung are an area supervised by the Provincial Government of DKI Jakarta, and it is managed by UPK PPUKMPP who is responsible to Industry, Trade, Cooperatives, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (PPKUKM) office of DKI Jakarta.

Sampling is done using non-probability sampling method. According to Sumarwan et al. (2018), non-probability sampling is sampling with each respondent who does not have the same opportunity using judgment sampling. Judgment sampling is a sampling technique based on the expertise of the subject being studied. In this case, the subjects being studied were customers or SMEs in the UPK PPUKMPP running their businesses in PIK area. The sample number was determined employing the Slovin formula that will be used to determine customer satisfaction and satisfaction of employee performance using a questionnaire tool.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N \cdot e^2}$$

Balanced Scorecard

The stages in implementing the Balanced Scorecard in UPK PPUKMPP were by describing the vision and mission of by the government agency into four perspectives of the Balanced Scorecard

which, then made a strategic map to obtain strategic objectives, and further preparing KPI through the interviews with management. The purpose of preparing KPI is as a measurement tool for achieving strategic goals. The preparation of KPI also involves four perspectives of the Balanced Scorecard. Those four perspectives are:

1. Financial Perspective

Measurement of a financial perspective was employed by calculating the level of budget effectiveness, the independence of the agency, and efficiency. It was carried out because UPK PPUKMPP received a budget from the Provincial Government of DKI Jakarta so that the measurement was considered to represent a financial perspective.

$$\text{BLUD Effectiveness Ratio} = \frac{\text{Realization of Revenue}}{\text{Target of Revenue}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Independence ratio} = \frac{\text{Revenue of BLUD}}{\text{Revenue of APBD}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{BLUD Efficiency Ratio} = \frac{\text{Realization of Expenditure}}{\text{Target of Expenditure}} \times 100\%$$

2. Customer Perspektive

The criterion used in assessing customer perspectives was by looking at the level of customer satisfaction with the service quality performed by UPK PPUKMPP. Service quality assessment was done by distributing questionnaires under service quality theory (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy). Furthermore, an assessment of the level of customer satisfaction was performed by comparing the value of perception and the value of expectations using a 5-scale representing very dissatisfied to very satisfied with a sample of 87 SMEs actors.

$$\text{Satisfaction} = \frac{\text{Perception}}{\text{Expectation}} \times 100\%$$

3. Internal Business Process Perspective

Measurement of the internal business process perspective was related to the role performed by UPK PPUKMPP in carrying out its activities to meet customer

needs. This perspective was related to the role of UPK PPUKMPP in objectifying activities following operational standards, such as the availability of adequate facilities

4. Learning and Growth Perspective

Measurement of this perspective was performed by assessing the level of employee satisfaction with company performance. The assessment of employee satisfaction level was carried out using a Minnesota questionnaire consisting of 20 questions. According to Wijaya (1997), the questionnaire measured the level of employee satisfaction with 20 types of questions relating to compensation, supervision, self-employment, teamwork, work safety, and opportunities to develop.

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The basic formula of AHP is the pairwise comparison of each criterion, and the results of the pairwise comparison are ranked for decision making. The assessment results are then processed using expert choice software. Saaty (2008) explained that after pairwise comparisons were performed, the consistency ratio or CR is under 10% or 0.1. The number of experts invited in this study was 3 people from UPK PPUKMPP and PPKUKMP Office of DKI Jakarta.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Financial Perspective

Realizing the Budget Revenue Targets

The calculation results of the effectiveness ratio of revenue stated that the effectiveness ratio of UPK PPUKMPP from 2017 to 2019 was included in the area with effective finance because UPK PPUKMPP can realize the budget revenue target. See on the below table:

Table1:BLUD Effectiveness Ratio

Years	Realization (IDR)	Target (IDR)	Effectiveness Ratio(%)
2017	4.563.864.000	4.563.864.000	100
2018	4.861.471.697	4.861.471.697	100
2019	5.001.902.527	5.001.902.527	100

The Independence Improvement of the Agency

From 2017 to 2019, BLUD revenue increased. However, it was also accompanied by an increase in the Regional Budget (APBD) having a proportion was greater than that of the increase in BLUD revenue so that the ratio of independence decreased from year to year. The decrease does not necessarily make UPK PPUKMPP having a low-performance achievement because the number of APBD received by the agency is adjusted to Expense Budget Proposal (RAB). However, UPK PPUKMPP of Pulogadung in 2019 reached an independence ratio of 59.81% meaning that it is included in the category of BLUD participatory in which the role of government is lower so that the agency is considered capable of developing and implementing program activities through the RAB. Following the administrative requirements for the implementation of the BLUD, it is stated that the improvement of independence is one of the objectives of the BLUD Financial Implementation Pattern so that the agency is expected to be able to improve the independence ratio. Agency implementing BLUD were expected to have a level of independence ratio above 50% because the purpose of establishing a BLUD is to reduce the agency's dependence on government assistance through APBD. See on the below table:

Table2: Independence Ratio

Years	Revenue of BLUD (IDR)	Revenue of APBD (IDR)	Independence Ratio (%)
2017	4.563.864.000	5.758.748.528	79,25
2018	4.861.471.697	7.730.020.482	62,89
2019	5.001.902.527	8.362.901.077	59,81

Realizing the Target Budget

The results showed that the budget in 2019 was more efficient than that in 2018 because UPK PPUKMPP was able to save a budget of 33.97%. However, if it is seen from the Budget Implementation Document (DPA), some programs that cannot be implemented because the budget for certain programs exceeds the budget. According to Nufriasa (2015), what should be considered in the absorption or the use of the budget is the achievement of maximum output in

using the budget. Therefore, the use of the budget can be maximized, so that it does not mean that when the budget is absorbed 100%, then the absorption or the use of the budget is maximized. See on the below table:

Table3: BLUD Efficiency Ratio

Years	Realization (IDR)	Target (IDR)	Efficiency Ratio (%)
2017	4.399.000.000	4.563.864.000	96,39
2018	4.409.664.995	4.861.471.697	90,71
2019	4.302.893.228	5.001.902.527	86,03

Customer Perspective Customer Satisfaction

Based on the results of the questionnaire regarding respondents' responses toward satisfaction of tangibility/physical evidence, 51% of respondents expressed satisfaction; toward reliability/fulfilling promises, 32% of respondents expressed satisfaction; toward responsiveness in providing services, 35% of respondents expressed satisfaction; toward service guarantees, 47% of respondents expressed satisfaction; and toward the empathy/understanding of customers, 49% of respondents expressed satisfaction.

Analysis of the Level of Customer Satisfaction

Analysis of the level of customer satisfaction is obtained by comparing the value of the perception score and the expectation score. The results of the level of satisfaction of respondents obtained from the tangibility dimension are 97.31%, the reliability dimension is 83.65%, the responsiveness dimension is 88.81%, the assurance dimension is 97.32%, and the empathy dimension is 100.24%. Overall, the level of customer satisfaction is 93.47% meaning that the customer is very satisfied with the services provided by UPK PPUKMPP of Pulogadung. However, the agency must continue to maintain and improve its services.

The Increase of Customers Number

Since the establishment of UPUK PPUKMPP of Pulogadung in 2009, it has 647 customers, and the number of customers is

stagnant from year to year. It is because the UPK PPUKMPP does not add work facilities for SMEs, and All active SMEs in the area of PIK of Pulogadung is allowed to continue their activities and rent work facilities without any time limit, and they must continue to extend their leasing business facilities annually. Therefore, through the results of customer satisfaction at the very satisfied level, UPK PPUKMPP can increase the potential of business locations by increasing the number of customers, so that more and more SMEs are helped. Ultimately, UPK PPUKMPP can improve the ability of SMEs and have an impact on providing employment, especially for the community around.

Internal Business Process Perspective Improvement of SMEs Training Event Quality

The training events are expected to be able to help SMEs to overcome problems in running their businesses. Besides, it is also expected to provide additional knowledge and information for customers or actors of SMEs. In their research results, Ardiyansah and Hartati also stated that (2016) the government needs to focus on facilitating SMEs in developing skills and increasing knowledge through intensive training events. Shamsuddoha et al. (2009) also explained that SMEs can achieve better international marketing performance through the formulation of proactive strategies in terms of knowledge and learning about international markets and assistance in creating competitive products.

It is in line with the strategic goals of the Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises in 2015-2019 stating that it is necessary to provide training to SMEs and facilitate the partnerships to improve competitiveness. Furthermore, Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises also stated that one of the challenges in developing SMEs is to increase capacity to establish partnerships and join global production and marketing networks so that

it is expected that UPK PPUKMP as the manager of PIK Area will be able to participate in facilitating partnership activities.

The improvement of Effective Business Processes

The land owned by UPUK PPUKMP of Pulogadung is approximately 106 hectares. However, currently, only around 30 hectares have been used, and 7 hectares are planned to be developed as residential areas. Extensive land ownership with maximum utilization of land will certainly help the SMEs development process. UPK PPUKMPP can build and provide supporting facilities, such as the addition of work & residential facilities, work barracks, as well as providing marketing facilities in PIK Area through collaboration with various parties. Pasaribu (2014), stated that BLUD agency can collaborate with other parties to improve the quality and quantity of services so that they do not burden agencies in improving services.

Improvement and Restoration of Facilities and Infrastructure

UPK PPUKMPP plans to build a parking area intended for large vehicles, both for buses and trucks. It is expected to help introduce SMEs in PIK area to be better known to the wider community. The availability of parking areas for trucks is also expected to help SMEs for loading and unloading goods. In addition, to support SMEs marketing activities, UPK PPUKMPP also renovated ten exhibition space units.

Learning & Growth Perspective Employee Satisfaction

The results showed that, overall, the highest level of employee satisfaction was at the satisfaction level of 41%, even though employees were feeling less satisfied by 7%. Overall, employee satisfaction is 77.03%, which means that employees are satisfied. The percentage of employees feeling less satisfied is due to no reward for tasks they have done. In this case, the

reward is in the form of gathering activities. Employees argued that a gathering should be held at least once a year to regain employee morale. However, there have been no more such activities for the last 3 years. It is in line with research conducted by Durst and DeSantis (1997) stating that organizations of the public sector need to identify the factors determining employee satisfaction so that policies concerning employee can be applied to retain and attract quality employees.

The Improvement of Human Resources Competence

The improvement of competency is performed by providing education and training for employees. However, the study results showed that employees were not interested in participating in training or educational activities. Whereas, competency and competent ability can help the process of service to customers for the better. Maarif (2010) stated that the improvement of the quality of human resources is a major requirement in the globalization era to realize competitiveness and independence, and it can make employees having the ability to compete, so as it can improve the service quality and high performance.

Simulation of Balanced Scorecard

There are two very low achievement categories in the simulation results of Balanced Scorecard. first is on the increase of the customer's number of KPI, and second is employee education & training activities of KPI. Both of these have low-performance achievements due to the number of facilities and markets owned by UPP PPUKMP of Pulogadung having not increased since last 10 years, so the number of customers tends to be stagnant which will certainly also affect agency revenue to be stagnant. Likewise, for the education & training activities of KPI, employees feel that Education and training activities are not an obligation for the employees. However, they feel that they can participate in educational activities or training both informal and formal at a higher level just if

they want. Employees are not interested in participating in these activities because they feel that education and training activities do not have a direct impact on the increase of income, so employees tend not to be interested in these activities. See on the below table

Table4:Performance Criteria

No	Interval (%)	Criteria (%)
1	91 ≤ 100	Very High
2	76 ≤ 90	High
3	66 ≤ 75	Moderate
4	51 ≤ 65	Low
5	≤ 50	Very Low

Source: Bappeda DKI Jakarta, 2018

Table5:Balanced Scorecard Simulation on UPK PPUKMPP Performance

No	KPI	Target	Actual	KPI Index (%)	Criteria
1	BLUD Effectiveness Ratio	100%	100%	100	Very High
2	Independence ratio	57%	59%	103	Very High
3	BLUD Efficiency Ratio	90%	86%	96	Very High
4	Customer Satisfaction Index	85%	93%	109	Very High
5	The Increase of Customers Number	5%	0%	0	Very Low
6	Number of attendees	75%	50%	67	Moderate
7	Land use according to the designation	30%	35%	117	Very High
8	Capacity of Facilities	10 unit	10 unit	100	Very High
9	Employee Satisfaction	80%	77%	96	Very High
10	Training or educational activities	2 employee	0	0	Very Low

Weighting the Perspective and KPI

As per result customer perspective has the greatest weight. Niven (2008) states that for government and non-profit organizations, the Balanced Scorecard has a main focus on the customer perspective because the government provides goods and services to serve customers. The development of SMEs in PIK area is expected to increase the competitiveness of SMEs through the efforts to improve the training quality of SME in line with the needs of SMEs actors and the improvement and addition of work facilities, so as those can increase the customer's number of and

the enrollment number of UPK PPUKMPP of Pulogadung. Therefore, SMEs in PIK area can enter and survive in market competition both domestic and global. Through the development of 7 hectares of land that will be designated as a residential area in an effective business process as a business process internal perspective, it is hoped that it can increase the opportunity of SMEs in PIK area to be better known by the wider community through infrastructure improvements, especially transportation, to facilitate access to PIK area be easier. See on the below table for the result:

Table6:Result of Weighting the Perspective and KPI

Perspective	Strategic Objectives	Weight (%)	Rank
Financial		7,7	
	Realizing the Budget Revenue Targets	1,2	10
	The Independence Improvement of the Agency	5,2	5
	Realizing the Target Budget	1,3	9
Customer		52,0	
	Customer Satisfaction	44,1	1
	The Increase of Customers Number	7,9	3
Internal Business Process		14,0	
	Improvement of SMEs Training Event Quality	3,1	8
	The Improvement of Effective Business Processes	4,5	7
	Improvement and Restoration of Facilities and Infrastructure	6,4	4
Learning & Growth		26,3	
	Employee Satisfaction	4,6	6
	The Improvement of Human Resources Competence	21,7	2

CONCLUSION

1. Agency needs to focus on the financial perspective by increasing the independence, on the customer perspective

by increasing customer satisfaction, on the internal business process perspective by improving effective business processes, and on the learning process and growth

perspective by increasing the competence of human resources.

2. In the effort to develop SMEs in the PIK area, the recommended program from strategic priorities to strategic objectives needs to focus on the customer perspective by continuing to improve customer satisfaction through providing convenience to financial access and holding regular meetings between agency and SMEs. In addition, it also focuses on increasing the competency of human resources to be able to manage PIK area which is in line with the vision of the agency. Likewise, the strategic goal of the increase in the customer number needs to be considered by making improvements to effective business processes.

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